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In search of 'European preference'. An overview of current initiatives that aim to reduce strategic dependency

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Amid the current geopolitical upheavals, crises and internal tensions facing Member States, the European Union has spent several years searching for a new economic doctrine. This doctrine — the set of principles and paradigms that shape the EU's market and policy instruments — has yet to be firmly established. Its conceptual and practical development remains a work in progress. Despite significant recent initiatives, such as the Compass for Competitiveness¹ and the Clean Industrial Act², the Union is struggling to draw the necessary conclusions from its interdependence with numerous third countries and global economic rivalries without breaking free completely from the paradigms on which its own market was built.

In these turbulent times, where the search for new instruments to consolidate the Union's industrial base is intertwined with the desire to avoid undermining international commitments, the principle of 'European preference' is being put forward as a relevant lever capable of safeguarding strategic sectors of the European economy. However, a brief analysis of current proposals highlights the difficulty of clearly defining the concept of 'European preference' and linking it to operational instruments. This conceptual and operational vagueness calls into question the credibility and effectiveness of a European preference in the context of current geo-economic challenges.

¹ COM (2025) 30 Final, A Competitiveness Compass for the EU, 29 January 2025

² COM (2025) 85 final, The Clean Industrial Deal: A joint roadmap for competitiveness and decarbonisation, 26 February 2025

I) References to European preference in recent sectoral texts

From a substantive perspective, the principle of 'European preference' has its origins in public procurement law. References to this principle date back quite some time; as early as the 1990s, when the Community ratified the GATT agreements, several positions in favour of a 'Buy European Act' were put forward as a counterpoint to the 'Buy American Act', which was introduced in 1993. However, it began to take on greater significance from 2012 onwards when a reciprocity instrument was proposed to restrict access to public procurement markets for operators from third countries³, which was not adopted until 2022 in the form of the International Procurement Instrument (IPI)⁴.

The avowedly strategic and geopolitical programme on which the current Commission has based its political agenda has resulted in an increased focus on the need to introduce into EU economic law a criteria of "European preference". Inspiration for this comes from the famous Letta report⁵, presented in April

³ COM (2012) 124 final of 21 March 2012, Proposal for a Regulation on the access of third-country products and services to the Union's internal market for public procurement and establishing procedures to facilitate negotiations on access for products and services of Union origin to the public procurement markets of third countries

⁴ Regulation 2022/1031 of 23 June 2022 on the access of third-country economic operators, goods and services to the Union's public procurement and concession markets and procedures supporting negotiations on access of Union economic operators, goods and services to the public procurement and concession markets of third countries (International Procurement Instrument – IPI)

⁵ E. Letta, "Much More Than a Market: speed, security, solidarity. Empowering the Single Market to deliver a sustainable future and prosperity for all EU Citizens", April 2024, available on:

2024, which called on institutions and Member States to adopt a more strategic approach to public procurement.

The principle of European preference has evolved from a technical instrument aimed at levelling the playing field in the awarding of public contracts into a key lever serving as both a bulwark against unfair competition and a safeguard to protect the internal market. Ursula Von der Leyen embraced this new direction as early as July 2024, stating in her policy address that a revision of the Public Procurement Directive will “will enable preference to be given to European products in public procurement for certain strategic sectors. It will help ensure EU added value for our citizens, along with security of supply for vital technologies, products and services. It will also modernise and simplify our public procurement rules, in particular with EU start-ups and innovators in mind.”⁶

However, beyond announcements and posturing, the implementation of the principle of European preference faces numerous obstacles linked to the diversity of applicable standards and the constraints of international commitments. Although this principle is not included in the public procurement directives (Directive 2014/24 on public contracts and Directive 2014/23 on concessions), recent legislation indirectly introduces it, albeit within clearly defined sectoral fields.

Two examples can be cited here.

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/ny3j24sm/much-more-than-a-market-report-by-enr-ico-letta.pdf>

⁶ U. von der Leyen, Political Guidelines for the next European Commission 2024–2029, available at: https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e6cd4328-673c-4e7a-8683-f63ffb2cf648_en?filename=Political%20Guidelines%202024-2029_EN.pdf.

Firstly, in the energy sector, there is the ‘net zero’ industry regulation⁷, which establishes a framework of measures to strengthen the European ecosystem for manufacturing ‘net-zero’ technology products. This text aims to improve the functioning of the internal market by ensuring the Union has access to a secure and sustainable supply of ‘net zero’ technologies. This will be achieved by increasing production capacities and supply chains for ‘net zero’ technologies, thus preserving their resilience while contributing to the Union’s climate objectives and climate neutrality goal. This regulation covers technologies defined as ‘net zero’, including those involved in energy production (e.g. solar, wind, batteries, heat pumps, hydrogen and nuclear power, as well as all forms of renewable energy) and all technologies involved in decarbonisation (e.g. CO₂ transport, clean propulsion systems and renewable fuels).

When awarding public contracts or concessions in these strategic sectors, contracting authorities must ensure that the value of the ‘net-zero’ technology supplied under a contract does not exceed 50% from a third country, and that the value of the components involved in the technology does not exceed this threshold either. However, this ‘community preference’ requirement does not apply to all third countries, but only to those that are not party to the WTO Agreement on Government Procurement (e.g. Russia, China and India). In practice, guidelines have been adopted to assess this dependency threshold on a project-by-project basis. These guidelines are rather complex to implement and evaluate the degree of

⁷ Regulation 2024/ 1735 of 13 June 2024 establishing a framework of measures to strengthen the European ecosystem for the manufacture of ‘net-zero’ technology products and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724, OJEU, L 2024/1735 of 28 June 2024

dependency and the market structure according to the net zero technology in question.⁸

Furthermore, in the defence sector, the European Union has recently increased the number of instruments aimed at pooling capabilities and strengthening joint procurement programmes for military equipment. These include the ASAP Regulation on support for ammunition production⁹, the EDIRPA Regulation¹⁰ on strengthening the defence industry through joint procurement, the SAFE Regulation¹¹ establishing financial assistance for urgent public investment in the defence sector, and the EDIP Regulation¹², which was

⁸ Commission Implementing Decision 2025/1100 of 23 May 2025 establishing guidelines for the implementation of certain selection criteria for strategic 'net-zero' projects set out in Article 13 of Regulation (EU) 2024/1735 of the European Parliament and of the Council, OJEU 18.6.2025.

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2023/1525 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 July 2023 on support for the production of ammunition (ASAP), OJEU of 24.7.2023, No 185/7 – the 'ASAP' Regulation was valid until 30 June 2025, but many of its provisions have been incorporated into the EDIRPA and EDIP Regulations

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2023/2418 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 on the establishment of an instrument to strengthen the European defence industry through joint procurement (EDIRPA), OJEU of 26 October 2023

¹¹ Council Regulation (EU) 2025/1106 of 27 May 2025 establishing the 'Acting for the Security of Europe by Strengthening the European Defence Industry' instrument (SAFE instrument), OJEU of 28 May 2025. It is worth noting that this Regulation is based on Article 122(1) TFEU, regarded as the 'emergency clause' in the Union's economic and monetary policy, allowing the Council of the Union to take appropriate measures in the event of a serious supply disruption of a product. This legal basis is, however, contested and the 'SAFE' Regulation is the subject of an action for annulment in proceedings currently pending before the Court of Justice (Case C-560/25, Parliament v Council)

¹² Regulation No 2025/2643 of 16 December 2025 establishing the Defence Industry Programme and a framework of measures to ensure the availability of defence products and

introduced in December 2025 and redefines the framework for supporting the defence industry within the Union. Without going into the technical details of these texts, they all encourage Member States to set up consortia to procure various types of defence equipment by supporting 'supply chains' made up of European companies.

II) **The affirmation of a more general approach to European preference : the proposal of an 'Industrial Accelerator Act'.**

This recent proposal¹³, made in early March 2026, forms part of the Commission's political programme and revives the institutions' well-established practice of defining broad, ten-year action strategies aimed at guiding the Union's activities in relation to several economic and political objectives.

The objective of the Industrial Accelerator Act is to increase the share of manufacturing in EU GDP from 14.3% in 2024 to 20% by 2035. However, a detailed examination of the proposal reveals that it does not formally recognise European preference as a general principle or cross-cutting requirement underpinning various areas of economic law, such as public procurement, state aid, and the control of foreign investment in strategic sectors. Overall, this proposal appears to be more of an instrument to support European industry by promoting products manufactured within the Union.

the timely supply of such products ('EDIP'), OJEU of 29.12.2025

¹³ COM (2026) 100 final, 4 March 2026, Proposal for a regulation establishing a framework of measures for the acceleration of industrial capacity and decarbonisation in strategic sectors

To achieve this, the Act relies on a combination of at least four instruments.

Firstly, the proposal includes an exclusion rule. If the IAA is passed, contracting authorities will be required to exclude certain tenders submitted by economic operators located in or controlled by third countries when awarding public contracts. However, this exclusion would apply only to certain product categories and only to operators established in states that have not concluded an international agreement with the EU guaranteeing access to public procurement markets. In practice, this exclusion is intended for operators based in China or India. This follows the significant ruling handed down by the Court of Justice in the so-called 'Kolin' case in November 2024¹⁴.

Second, the promotion of 'Made in the EU' is further characterised by the introduction of an obligation to purchase products originating in the Union, as defined in the Customs Code¹⁵. From 2029, this obligation will apply to the award of certain works and supply contracts and will also indirectly apply to the state aid regime. In practice, contracting authorities and entities will be required to 'apply the requirements relating to Union origin and low-carbon requirements' (Article 11 of the proposal) for certain product categories (primarily steel, aluminium, and concrete), alongside the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM).

Third, regarding state aid, the European preference would take the form of an earmarking requirement to

strengthen strategic value chains for activities considered essential from an industrial perspective. In practice, this would mean that a proportion of the national budget allocated to state aid, ranging from 45% to 100%, would have to be directed towards supporting certain sectors, notably the production of electric vehicles which are produced in Europe (or whose main components are originating from EU) (Article 12 of the proposal). A similar approach is also emerging for screening foreign investments. It is therefore envisaged that foreign investments (> €100 million) in batteries, electric vehicles (EVs), solar photovoltaic (PV) systems and critical raw materials should employ a minimum of 50% EU workers and ensure local supply chains.

Finally, the proposal introduces stricter requirements for certain goods, particularly electric vehicles. In such cases, public support, whether in the form of public procurement or state aid, would be conditional upon the product being assembled within the EU (rule of origin), as well as upon a proportion of essential components, such as batteries, being manufactured in Europe, or upon other equipment meeting low-carbon requirements. Annex III of the proposed regulation contains very detailed provisions on the European production requirement for electric vehicles. These include the vehicle being assembled within the Union, the ratio of the total ex-works price of vehicle components originating in the Union (excluding the battery) to the total ex-works price of all components (excluding the battery) being at least 70%, and the vehicle's traction battery containing at least three main specific components. This highly technical level of detail could cause issues with implementation at the contract award stage.

Therefore, rather than basing the text on a general principle of European preference, it is instead based on a set

¹⁴ CJEU, 22 October 2024, Kolin, Case C-652/22.

¹⁵ Regulation (EU) No 952/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 October 2013 laying down the Union Customs Code

of sector-specific instruments aimed at supporting certain industrial value chains.

III) A principle of European preference under structural constraints

The recognition of a general principle of European preference, which would imply systematic prioritisation of European operators in the award of public procurement contracts or in state aid funding, faces several constraints.

The first relates to compliance with the Union's international commitments. Through its membership of the WTO and the conclusion of numerous new-generation trade agreements including substantial chapters on public procurement and investment, the EU regards compliance with international commitments as integral to its identity. However, unless these commitments are disregarded, the introduction of a general preference or express derogations would contradict well-established principles such as non-discrimination and equal treatment. Indeed, the clauses set out in the agreements' chapters extend rules contained in the directives to third countries. These rules are often more precise than those in the WTO Agreement on Government Procurement. Examples include technical specifications, participation rules, and supplier qualification conditions. In Opinion 2/15¹⁶, the Court of Justice of the EU held that, as these access arrangements are based on non-discrimination, transparency, and efficiency, they are likely to directly and immediately affect trade in goods and services between the parties.

¹⁶ Opinion 2/15 delivered by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) on 16 May 2017, *Free trade agreement with Singapore*.

This means that the proposed Industrial Accelerator Act treats products originating in states that have concluded trade agreements or are parties to the WTO as equivalent to those produced within the Union. According to Article 8 of the proposal, 'products originating in third countries with which the Union has concluded an agreement establishing a free trade area or a customs union, or which are parties to the Agreement on Government Procurement (WTO GPA), where relevant Union obligations exist under that agreement, shall be considered as originating in the Union'. By treating products originating in third countries covered by free trade agreements (e.g. Canada, Japan, and, in the future, Mercosur) as 'originating in the Union', the proposal prioritises compliance with the principles of non-discrimination and equality in international economic law, as well as respect for trade commitments, even if these are severely undermined or ignored by certain partners, over a more assertive approach to European preference that is more explicitly focused on supporting products that originate strictly within the Union. By prioritising compliance with all international commitments, the IAA dilutes and obscures the scope of the concept of European preference. A key issue that will influence the debate on this proposal is the extent to which reciprocity is balanced.

The proposal provides for exceptions to equivalence – notably where a third country has failed to provide national treatment in relation to Union products or entities, or where an exclusion is justified to avoid dependencies or any other developments that may threaten the Union's security of supply of the products. However, the scope of these exceptions remains rather vague. The extent to which the European preference is diluted within international agreements or applied

more strictly will depend on how these exceptions are defined and interpreted.

A second constraint relates to the capacity to support European industry and decarbonisation. It must be made clear that this text is not a roadmap to carbon neutrality. In the spirit of the Draghi report, it considers decarbonisation and strategic autonomy together, but environmental ambitions remain limited to so-called 'strategic' sectors and their decarbonisation. There is no mention of the impacts on other planetary boundaries. Resource efficiency in industrial processes and materials is essential for reducing our economic dependencies, yet it is not mentioned. Many sectors are not covered by the texts, including the plastics industry, as well as fertilisers and heavy transport. The Clean Industrial Act's quantitative approach, with its stated target of 20% of industrial production in European GDP, illustrates traditional political planning methods. As emphasised, "what matters is not producing more, but producing what we need using fewer resources, creating more sustainable products and more circular value chains whilst reducing our dependencies"¹⁷.

Finally, a third constraint will be political in nature. The perception of European preference varies from one Member State to another because each has a different industrial base and a different level of dependence on third countries (and on China). Member States must also accommodate their trading partners in order to safeguard their own markets. A recent French High Commission for Strategy and Planning report shows that up to 55%

¹⁷ V. M. Péron, M. Dupré, W. Kalinowski, 'What tools for a sustainable European industrial policy?', Veblen Institute Note, December 2025, available at <https://www.veblen-institute.org/Quels-outils-pour-une-politique-industrielle-europeenne-durable.html>

of the European Union's manufacturing output within the internal market could be exposed to unsustainable Chinese competition in the medium term¹⁸.

The level of exposure varies greatly from country to country: it is around 70% in Germany, 60% in Italy, 50% in Spain, and 36% in France. The interests of Member States with regard to suppliers from these countries are not the same: to avoid an even greater loss of business and jobs, some Member States, including Germany, are reluctant to advocate a strict European preference, as this would lead to retaliatory measures from China. Pursuing a European preference is thus at the crossroads of global transformations, reflecting both geopolitical turbulence and the evolution of European economic law paradigms.

¹⁸ See for instance, Haut Commissariat au Plan: "L'industrie européenne face au rouleau compresseur chinois", available on: <https://www.strategie-plan.gouv.fr/publications/lindustrie-europeenne-face-au-rouleau-compresseur-chinois>

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